

Giant Pituitary PINET: Follow-up and Evolution

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ABSTRACT

Pituitary adenomas, currently called pituitary neuroendocrine tumors, are unpredictable tumors. We present a 45-years-old female with a transsellar resection of macro-PA history. She began with amenorrhea and was discharged without therapeutic indications and remained asymptomatic for 9 years, that evolved rapidly, invading neighboring structures, showing aggressive behavior.

Keywords: Pituitary adenoma; Giant pituitary adenoma; Non-functioning pituitary adenoma; Aggressive-invasive pituitary adenoma; Follow-up.

Abbreviations: Pituitary tumours (PT); Pituitary adenomas (PA); giant PAs (GPAs); pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (PitNET); World Health Organization Classification (WHO); Central Nervous (CNS); Health Organization Classification of Endocrine and Neuroendocrine Tumors (ENET)

INTRODUCTION

Pituitary adenomas, namely pituitary neuroendocrine tumors (PitNETs), are a heterogeneous group of neoplasms deriving from the neuroendocrine cell of the pituitary cells are mostly benign lesions of the CNS and account for 7-17% of intracranial neoplasms^[1]. According to their size, PAs are classified as: microadenomas (<1 cm), macroadenomas (1-3 cm), and giant PAs (GPAs) which are tumors >4 cm in diameter with a frequency of 5-15% and 54.3% has been classified as non-functional (NF) (not associated to hormonal hypersecretion syndrome)^[1-4]. In Mexico the average PA age presentation is 49 years with a frequency of 62% in women and 70% of PA are NF^[5]. Approximately 25-55% of PA are invasive and 2.7-15% aggressive characterized by surrounding tissue's massive invasion, rapid growth, large size, recurrence, treatment resistance, high mitotic index, Ki67 index > 3% and extensive expression of p53^[6].

While usually benign, pituitary tumours sporadically exhibit hostile behavior, with rapid growth, invasion of surrounding tissues, multiple recurrences also resistance to conventional treatments.

The recently revised fifth edition of the World Health Organization (WHO) classifications (2021)^[7], and the World Health Organization Classification of Endocrine and Neuroendocrine Tumors (2022) revealed significant changes to the classification of PAs, the most common type of PTs. This change categorized pituitary adenomas as neuroendocrine tumors and proposed the name to be revised to pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (PitNET)^[8].

The aim of this work was a report a natural history of an aggressive giant pituitary adenoma.

CLINICAL CASE

45-years-old female with a transsellar resection of macro-PA history. She was discharged without therapeutic indications and remained asymptomatic for 9 years, when she began with amenorrhea. The patient arrives at emergency service for oppressive hemicranial headache (7/10), decreased visual acuity, blurry vision and congestive nasal

sensation, with 7 months of evolution. On physical examination, she was oriented in its three spheres, with left eye visual field decreased by campimetry, without cardiopulmonary commitment, assign logical abdomen, and whole limbs. Simple nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) showed a sellar lesion measuring 4.0 x 4.9 x 5.2 cm with invasion of adjacent structures on both sides (cavernous, sphenoid, and ethmoid sinuses), that was classified as Hardy Vezina grade IVD, KNOSP grade IV being compatible with a GPA (Figure 1A) for which the protocol for the management of PA was started.

Endocrinology service starts therapeutic management with 50 mg of prednisone. Laboratory studies reports: prolactin (PRL) 24 ng/ml, diluted PRL 18 ng/ml, T4L 1.1 ng/dL. Ophthalmology diagnosed VI right cranial nerve (CN) paralysis, chiasmatic syndrome and bitemporal hemianopsy. The GPA resection was performed 1 month later using a right pretemporal transcranial approach. Neurosurgery reported: bleeding of 1000cc during the intervention. Histopathological analysis confirmed the diagnosis of neuroendocrine tumor type PA (Figure 1D), with IHC positivity to FSH, expression of p53 and Ki67 index of 32.6%. (Figure 2A-D).

During post-surgical evolution the patient presented occasional headache, right III CN paralysis, diabetes insipidus (DI) episode and FT4 of 7.19 ng/dL, for which treatment with desmopressin, prednisone and levothyroxine was started, later she was discharged because of clinical improvement.

Four months after surgery, the follow-up MRI reported: an important residual lesion measuring 3.8x 4.1x 3.6 cm (Figure 1B) and due to the fact that the size of the tumor was within the limits of the established dimensions^[7], a complementary surgical resection was raised, so the skull base surgery service schedule, her for transsphenoidal surgery.

In the last two follow-up endocrinology consultations, the patient reported 17 months of evolution of amenorrhea without other symptoms and laboratory studies showed FT4 9.7 pmol/L, TSH 0.015 μ IU/mL, LH 0.26 mIU/mL, FSH 2.9 mIU/mL, estradiol 13.633 pg/mL, PRL 1.4 ng/mL, and cortisol 0.4 μ g/dL. With this hormonal profile (thyrotroph, corticotroph and DI) it was considered that in relation to NF-GPA the patient had adequate treatment, regarding the amenorrhea, it was decided to start hormonal treatment and the control MRI showed no changes compared to the previous one. (Figure 1C). The patient continued with control follow-up pending for a new surgery.

Giant pituitary adenomas comprise 5-15% of all pituitary tumors. It has been reported that 54.3-85.7%^[9] correspond to the NF type, postoperative mortality of 35% and can present at advanced ages^[3,4]. Silent NFPAs are not associated with clinical hypersecretion syndromes but they can show hormonal activity^[7]. NF gonadotropic PAs can be highly infiltrative and aggressive, as they are clinically silent until they are big in size and invade adjacent structures^[6]. PAs immunochemistry evaluation is essential to

determine hormonal secretory activity and its aggressiveness detected by cell proliferation markers expression (Ki67 and p53), besides the evaluation of its size and invasion of surrounding structures^[2,6].

D)

E)

F)

G)

Figure 1. Pituitary magnetic resonance imaging: A) MRI showing sellar lesion with solid appearance and irregular morphology, defined and lobulated contours, sella turcica floor destruction, invasion to left cavernous sinus (CS), sphenoid sinus (SS), ethmoidal sinus body (ES), posterior ethmoidal cells (PEC) choanae (CH), displacement of the optic chiasm (OC), and cavernous portion of the homolateral internal carotid artery (ICA). B) Post- Surgical GPA. Residual tumor in the sellar and suprasellar region with invasion to right CS, ES, OC, temporal lobe, sellar and parasellar region involvement; C) Residual GPA. Sellar and suprasellar tumor with predominant right CS invasion, ES, PEC and CH region. GPA Photomicrographs.

Figure 2. Histopathological features. (A) the tumor with loss of lobulated, dense, monotonous, polygonal pattern, eosinophilic cytoplasm, basophilic nucleus, with absence of mitosis) (H&Ex400). B) Evidence of cytoplasmic expression of FSH, (C) Nuclear expression for p53 protein and in (D) Observed nuclear expression of Ki67 (IHC staining original magnification 400x).

DISCUSSION

For this subgroup, the term “aggressive pituitary adenoma” was used; in 2017, the acronym PitNETs was suggested for all pituitary adenomas^[7], importance the need to regulate the benign or aggressive nature of each one of them and accentuating the heterogeneity of the biological and clinical behavior of these lesions^[7]. Aggressive PitNETs are characterized by dissemination to extrasellar regions, with rapid tumor growth, high hormonal serum levels, and resistance to treatments (medical therapy, surgery, or radiotherapy), decisive high morbidity and mortality. The prognosis of these tumors severely depends on their biology, and the search for reliable clinical and pathological markers as predictors of tumor behavior.

Recently, developments in molecular biology and bioinformatics have permissible a more detailed considerate of tumorigenesis in aggressive PitNETs done specific essential genes, enrolment in diverse molecular pathways, regulators, and effects of the tumoral microenvironment with involved in aggressive PitNETs, describing the potential target therapies. The molecular mechanisms linked to PitNETs' aggressiveness and invasiveness is crucial. With the aim to the identified new biomarkers for prognostic stratification and the development of novel therapies.

The treatment of choice for NFPAs (except prolactinomas) is surgical removal of the tumor and in the case of GPA's, the transcranial route is preferred, due to the size and the high risk of complications such as its proximity to the arteries, which make resection of the tumor difficult^[9-11]. Visual improvement is one of the main objectives of surgery, and in 43-99% of cases have shown favorable results^[3]. In our patient, visual improvement was the main objective owing to the high risk of intraoperative bleeding. Lateral

extension towards the cavernous sinus (CS), although rare, is associated with CN paralysis, like in this case in which the patient developed paralysis of the III and VI right CN; these are the two most affected CN in said complication^[9].

In giant pituitary adenomas, it has been reported that the extent of surgical resection is the main factor for recurrence or progression, with partial resection being the most associated with tumor recurrence and progression^[12]. Around 18% of PA surgeries have poor results due to residual lesion and pituitary apoplexy, these conditions represent up to 9.2% of the causes of surgical reintervention^[4]; From 4.2-23.2% of postoperative mortality patients has been related to incomplete tumor resection, causing tumor inflammation and compression of adjacent vital structures. Furthermore, pituitary apoplexy occurs in up to 50% of patients with reoperation of which up to 50% die^[4]. All these reports make the patient an exceptional case since despite the tumor aggressiveness, surgeries number and complications that she presented her condition has been controllable.

GPAs are underestimated by the medical community; however, they are usually persistent and relapsing after surgery, this changes the strategy to follow for their care. For these it has been recommended to realize complete protocol with histopathological study and IHC technique to determine the parameters requested by the WHO, these have potential implications regarding medical treatment and follow-up^[7].

CONCLUSION

This case is a clear example of the complications that can occur when for some reason (medical or patient) it is not possible to carry out an adequate approach and follow-up of the tumor, hence the importance of individualizing each case.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

D.N.B., R.G.R., D.M.Ch.M., N.V.C., A.R., M.T.S., D.R.B., A.O.P.: substantially contributed to conceptualization, design, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation; drafting, revising it and final approval of the version to be published.

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